

Introduction

- **Cold roll forming** is a continuous process aiming for progressive bending of sheet metal using stations with rotating rolls without changing material thickness;
- The **racking systems** installed in warehouses are almost exclusively made of thin-walled cold-formed sections;
- **Fatigue design rules** for cold formed steel sections are missing on a European level - **FASTCOLD project** aims at developing these rules.

Objectives

- Evaluate the distribution and magnitude of **residual stresses** for two profiles (**U-channel and Z-section**) due to the roll forming process;
- Apply **mechanical cyclic loads** in the simulation models (U-channel and Z-section). Study the influence of existing residual stresses (due to the roll forming process) combined with external cyclic loads on the **fatigue resistance of the profiles**.

Results and Discussion

1. Materials and Profiles

The numerical simulations were performed using **COPRA® FEA RF** finite element software. Two steel (**S350GD**) profiles – **U-channel** profile and **Z-section** profile (rail section) – were analysed.

Fig. 1. Dimensions [mm] of the U-channel and Z-section profile (length=520mm).

2. Residual Stresses Distribution (after the roll forming process)

Fig. 2. Nonlinear through the thickness residual stress distribution in corner regions of thin sheets: (a) theoretical solution; (b) numerical results for the Z-section profile.

3. Fatigue Analysis – Number of Cycles until Failure

An **external cyclic mechanical load** was applied to the cold roll formed profile in order to determine the **resulting stress range** and the **critical area** where **fatigue cracks** nucleation tends to occur.

Fig. 3. External cyclic load applied in the flanges of both profiles.

Fig. 4. Stresses in the critical node for a maximum mechanical cyclic load applied of 9 kN (Z-section profile).

Table 1. Estimated number of cycles for three different cyclic loads applied in the large flange of the Z-section profile using the local S-N based approach.

Load [kN]	σ_{max} [MPa]	σ_{min} [MPa]	σ_m [MPa]	$\Delta\sigma$ [MPa]	N_f
2	406.20	167.85	287.03	238.35	1.2E+08
4.5	511.81	-27.02	242.40	538.83	2.7E+04
9	631.16	-359.60	135.78	990.76	140

4. Fatigue Analysis – Fatigue Endurance Limit

According to EN 1993-1-9 (2005), the number of cycles for which the structure is considered to have an infinite life is 5 millions.

Fig. 5. Maximum load for 5 million cycles.

Conclusion

Roll Forming Process

Residual stress distributions in the corner regions obtained after simulating the roll forming process are similar to the theoretical solution. However 3D effects may disturb this theoretical solution, requiring FEA.

Fatigue Analysis

Critical nodes:

- Located in the corner regions and the most distant from where the load was applied;

Number of cycles until failure:

- A **stress relaxation** after the first cycle was observed. The second cycle showed no variations of the maximum and minimum stresses, proving an **elastic behaviour** of the material in the second cycle justifying a stress based **S-N approach**;
- **Low cycle fatigue** for an applied load of 9 kN → S-N approach is not suitable. Change the **hardening rule**: isotropic to **kinematic** is required.

Fatigue endurance limit:

- Higher maximum loads were expected for the Z-section profile since this structure was designed to present higher stiffness. However the variations might occur due to the difference in the FE meshes and the location where the load was applied.

Acknowledgments